

Answers to Frequently Asked Questions about “Estimating Excess Mortality Due to Female Genital Mutilation” (Ghosh, Flowe, & Rockey, 2024)

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Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting (FGM/C) poses serious health risks, yet its impact on mortality has been difficult to quantify due to data limitations and intersecting social disadvantages. In our study, “Estimating Excess Mortality Due to Female Genital Mutilation”, we used the best available demographic data to show that FGM/C is a leading cause of death among affected girls and young women, with an estimated one death occurring every 12 minutes. Through rigorous robustness checks, we demonstrate that this mortality effect cannot be explained by alternative factors such as socioeconomic status, healthcare access, or general differences in mortality trends across countries.

As authors of this study, we have had the privilege of presenting our findings to a wide range of professionals working in this area worldwide, including researchers, policymakers, healthcare providers, and human rights advocates. During these discussions, we have been asked many important questions about our methodology, findings, and implications. Here, we provide answers to the most frequently asked questions, addressing key methodological concerns and clarifying the significance of our research.

Why were these specific countries chosen for the research? E.g. why were Somalia/Somaliland not included in the sample despite the near universal FGM/C prevalence rate?

The countries in our study were selected based on the availability of high-quality data from the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS). These surveys provide detailed information on FGM/C prevalence and the age at which it occurs. Somalia/Somaliland, despite its high FGM/C prevalence, was not included because it lacks recent, comprehensive DHS data that meets our study's requirements. However, we did use alternative data from the Orchid Project to include additional countries in our robustness checks.

Is there a reason that Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys were not considered, in addition to the DHS, to expand the country list?

While both MICS and DHS use similar methodologies, DHS surveys tend to have more consistent and standardized question wording across countries. MICS surveys sometimes introduce slight variations, which can make cross-country comparisons more challenging.

MICS surveys often have fewer questions specifically related to FGM. For instance, they may collect basic information on prevalence but provide less detail on aspects such as age at cutting, who performed the procedure, and the specific type of FGM.

Was mortality fully implied from the UN Population Division data on population by age, or did they also include standardized mortality estimates for instance from the UN IGME?

Mortality was fully implied from the UN data by age and sex.

Can you share with us the number of deaths per country?

These are available upon request.

The number of annual deaths you've noted indicates about a 1% mortality rate - noting about 4 million girls are cut each year per UNICEF estimates. How do you reflect on how this compares to prior existing estimates of mortality due to FGM/C (for instance 1 in 500 which has been published in the past)

Our empirical strategy is intentionally conservative and cautious, designed to rule out alternative explanations that might confound the observed mortality effects. Specifically, we account for:

- Country- and year-specific transitory conditions (e.g., droughts, conflicts, epidemics) that could disproportionately affect female mortality rates.
- Household-level gendered differences in access to nutrition and healthcare, ensuring that our observed effects are not driven by pre-existing disparities in child mortality unrelated to FGM/C.
- Robust statistical controls to differentiate between FGM/C-specific effects and broader systemic risks affecting child survival in certain regions.

Given the significant divergence between historical estimates (1 in 500) and more recent figures suggesting a potential 1% mortality rate, it is critical to reassess FGM/C mortality risk with the most up-to-date, population-representative data. Our cautious empirical approach aims to provide the most accurate and conservative estimates possible, ensuring that any observed mortality effects are directly attributable to FGM/C rather than external confounding factors.

Are you planning to expand the list of countries?

We are certainly interested in expanding our analysis to more countries as high-quality data becomes available. In our robustness checks, we already included additional countries using data from the Orchid project. Future research could focus on gathering more comprehensive data from countries not currently included in the DHS surveys.

What do you think are the key limitations of this research?

Some key limitations include:

- We can't be certain that all excess deaths are directly caused by FGM/C.
- Our results likely underestimate the total impact as we don't consider long-term consequences like obstetric complications.
- The estimate is based on average effects across countries, which may not reflect the situation in individual countries accurately.
- Our data on FGM/C prevalence may not capture recent changes in practice.

Do these data include only immediate post-FGM/C deaths or also factors in later deaths, e.g. during childbirth, etc.?

Our study primarily captures deaths that occur around the time of FGM/C or shortly after. Long-term consequences, such as deaths during childbirth later in life, are not included in our estimates. This means our results are very likely conservative.

GM types/severity and consequences varies to death. Treating consequences equally and using population size may drive estimates upwards.

While we attempt to control for country-specific factors, our analysis necessarily treats FGM/C as a single practice. This is an inherent challenge in large-scale mortality estimation; **however, our robustness checks help mitigate concerns about potential overestimation due to variations in FGM types and severity.**

Specifically, we address the concern in two key ways in our paper:

1. Assessing the Influence of Individual Countries
 - To rule out the possibility that our results are driven by a single country—particularly one where a specific form of FGM is predominant—we conduct a robustness check. We systematically re-estimate our results while excluding one country at a time. Our findings remain largely unchanged, indicating that no single country is disproportionately driving the overall estimates.
2. Alternative Weighting Approaches
 - We report results both weighted by population and with each country treated equally. The latter approach, while ensuring that the estimates are not disproportionately influenced by the largest countries (e.g., Ethiopia, Nigeria), has the drawback of giving greater statistical weight to smaller African countries. This trade-off highlights the challenge of balancing representativeness and robustness in cross-national FGM mortality estimates. Nevertheless, the results are consistent across weighting approaches.

FGM survivors often face multiple intersecting disadvantages, such as lower socioeconomic status (SES), reduced access to healthcare, and broader systemic inequalities, all of which could contribute to morbidity and mortality. This complexity makes it challenging to directly attribute increased mortality to FGM/C alone.

This very challenge is the motivation for our study. Because FGM/C survivors experience multiple disadvantages, it is indeed difficult to isolate its direct impact on mortality. To address this, our approach leverages differences in the incidence and timing of FGM/C across countries and utilizes the best available data on both FGM/C prevalence and age-, sex-, and year-specific mortality rates. This allows us to control for many of these confounding factors and isolate mortality differences.

For any alternative explanation to account for the observed differences in mortality, it would have to coincide precisely with the age at which FGM/C is typically performed. The age distribution of FGM/C varies across countries, yet despite these variations, the mortality patterns we observe align closely with the ages at which FGM/C is most commonly practiced. Moreover, when we compare age-specific mortality rates within countries between girls and boys, we find that the excess mortality effect is specific to girls, further ruling out other potential explanations.

Ultimately, based on our analysis, the only convincing explanation for the observed differences in mortality that we are aware of is FGM/C itself.

Is it possible to work out how many deaths occur that are not immediate?

While our current methodology doesn't allow us to estimate non-immediate deaths, this is an important area for future research. It would require long-term follow-up studies and more detailed health data from the affected countries.

How does the death toll from FGM/C compare to other leading causes of death among girls in the affected countries?

Our estimates suggest that FGM/C is responsible for more deaths of girls than any other single cause in the countries we studied, including diseases like HIV/AIDS, measles, and malaria. However, it's important to note that these comparisons are based on our statistical estimates and this should be kept in mind.

What could have been specific health complications from FGM/C that directly contribute to these deaths? Can you give an example/examples?

Common complications that can lead to death include severe bleeding (haemorrhage), infections (including tetanus and sepsis), and shock. In some cases, the use of unsterilized instruments can also lead to the transmission of diseases like HIV.

What are the long-term health impacts of FGM/C on survivors who do not die from the procedure? Does the research shed light on this aspect?

While our research focuses on mortality, other studies have shown that FGM/C survivors often face long-term health issues including chronic pain, urinary problems, increased risk of obstetric complications, and psychological trauma. Our study doesn't directly address these long-term impacts, and we acknowledge their importance in understanding the full impact of FGM/C.

Are the estimates skewed by data quality? For example, could the results be affected by over/under-reporting in certain countries?

We addressed these concerns in several ways:

- **Data Quality:** We utilized the highest quality data available to minimize measurement noise, drawing from United Nations population statistics and the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS).
- **Statistical Controls:** While some degree of error is inevitable in any dataset, it would need to be specifically correlated with sex-specific mortality at particular ages to significantly impact our estimates. Our statistical approaches were designed to account for and control for potential measurement error.
- **Conservative Estimates:** Any non-sex-specific measurement error would actually lead to *attenuation bias*, meaning our estimates are very likely to underestimate. This gives us more confidence in our findings, as any bias would make our results more conservative rather than overstated.

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References

Ghosh, A., Flowe, H., & Rockey, J. (2023). Estimating excess mortality due to female genital mutilation. *Scientific Reports*, *13*(1), Article 13328. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-38276-6>